

WASM Plugin System for Database Proxy with Sandboxed Host Functions and Hot Reload

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Abstract

We present a WebAssembly (WASM) plugin system for a database proxy enabling user-supplied extensibility for authentication, query transformation, caching, routing, and metrics via sandboxed WASM modules. The system uses Wasmtime for WASM execution with a capability-based permission model (12 distinct permissions), configurable resource limits (memory, CPU timeout, filesystem access), hot-reloading of plugins without proxy restart, and a host function API providing database-specific operations (query execution, cache access, schema discovery, metrics recording). While WASM extensibility exists in network proxies (Envoy proxy-wasm, Istio), its application to database proxies with database-specific host functions and a granular capability-based permission model is novel. PostgreSQL and MySQL use native C/C++ extensions that lack sandboxing and crash the server on bugs.

Keywords: WebAssembly, WASM, Plugin System, Database Proxy, Sandboxing, Hot Reload, Capability-Based Security, Wasmtime

1 Background and Prior Art

Envoy Proxy (proxy-wasm): WASM filter support for network proxy extensibility. Defines proxy-wasm ABI for HTTP/TCP filters. No database-specific host functions (no query execution, no cache access, no schema discovery).

Istio WASM Plugins: Built on Envoy’s proxy-wasm. Service mesh focused. No database awareness.

PostgreSQL Extensions: Native C extensions loaded via `CREATE EXTENSION`. No sandboxing – a bug in an extension crashes the server. No hot reload – requires server restart. No resource limits.

MySQL Plugins: Native C++ plugin API. Same limitations as PostgreSQL: no sandboxing, no hot reload, server crashes on plugin bugs.

Spin/Fermyon: WASM application platform. General-purpose, not database-specific. No database host functions.

2 Technical Contribution

2.1 Capability-Based Permission Model

Each plugin declares required permissions in its manifest. The proxy validates permissions before loading:

```

1 enum Permission {
2     QueryExecute,    // Execute SQL on backend
3     CacheRead,      // Read from proxy cache
4     CacheWrite,     // Write to proxy cache
5     HttpFetch,     // Make outbound HTTP requests
6     Crypto,        // Access cryptographic functions
7     KvRead,        // Read from key-value store
8     KvWrite,       // Write to key-value store
9     Metrics,       // Record custom metrics
10    ConfigRead,    // Read proxy configuration
11    Network,      // General network access
12    FilesystemRead, // Read filesystem (restricted paths)
13    FilesystemWrite, // Write filesystem (restricted paths)
14 }

```

A plugin requesting only `QueryExecute` and `Metrics` cannot access the cache, filesystem, or network. This is enforced at the Wasmtime runtime level – host functions for denied capabilities return permission errors.

2.2 Resource Limits

```

1 struct SandboxLimits {
2     max_memory_bytes: usize,          // default: 16MB
3     max_execution_time: Duration,    // default: 100ms per invocation
4     max_fuel: u64,                   // Wasmtime fuel metering
5     filesystem_root: Option<PathBuf>, // sandboxed filesystem root
6     allowed_hosts: HashSet<String>, // for HTTP requests
7 }

```

Wasmtime’s fuel metering provides deterministic CPU limiting independent of wall-clock time.

2.3 Database-Specific Host Functions

```

1 // Host functions exposed to WASM plugins via Wasmtime linker
2 fn host_query_execute(sql: &str) -> Result<QueryResult>;
3 fn host_cache_get(key: &str) -> Option<Vec<u8>>;
4 fn host_cache_set(key: &str, value: &[u8], ttl_secs: u32);
5 fn host_metrics_increment(name: &str, value: f64);
6 fn host_log(level: LogLevel, message: &str);
7 fn host_schema_get(table: &str) -> Option<TableSchema>;
8 fn host_config_get(key: &str) -> Option<String>;

```

These host functions are the key differentiation from Envoy’s proxy-wasm: they provide database-specific operations that enable plugins to make intelligent decisions based on query content, cached results, and schema metadata.

2.4 Hot Reload

The plugin loader watches configured directories for new or updated WASM binaries. On detection:

- Validate new binary (check WASM magic bytes, verify manifest)
- Pre-compile via Wasmtime (ahead-of-time compilation)
- Atomically swap the plugin instance (old instance drains pending requests, new instance handles new requests)
- Old instance is dropped after drain timeout

No proxy restart required. Active connections are not interrupted.

2.5 Plugin Hook Points

Plugins register for lifecycle hooks:

Hook	Timing	Use Case
<code>on_connect</code>	Client connects	Custom authentication
<code>pre_query</code>	Before query execution	Query transformation, access control
<code>post_query</code>	After query execution	Result transformation, logging
<code>on_routing</code>	Before routing decision	Custom routing logic
<code>on_cache_miss</code>	Cache miss detected	External cache lookup
<code>on_error</code>	Query error	Custom error handling

3 Implementation

Implemented in Rust using Wasmtime. Module: `plugins/` with sub-modules: `config.rs`, `runtime.rs` (Wasmtime integration), `loader.rs` (WASM binary loading + manifest validation), `host_functions.rs` (linker setup), `sandbox.rs` (permission + resource enforcement), `hot_reload.rs` (file watcher + atomic swap), `metrics.rs`. Total: 748+ LOC in `mod.rs`. Licensed under SSPL-1.0.